

The EV Cyber Kill Chain: From Charging Port to Cloud — Attacks, Missed Signals, and What Industry Must Fix Next

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Abstract—The electric-vehicle (EV) ecosystem has evolved into a large-scale cyber-physical system that tightly couples vehicles with charging equipment (EVSE), backend control planes, roaming/payment services, and utility/building networks. Recent measurement studies and public disclosures indicate that security mechanisms assumed by standards are frequently absent or inconsistently deployed in real deployments, leaving practical attack paths open across layers and stakeholders.

This paper systematizes the state of the art in research and the incident landscape by presenting a structured view of attack progression, showing how weaknesses at the charging port, PLC/PHY and negotiation layers, EVSE control planes, and cloud/API surfaces can be chained to produce real-world outcomes, from charging disruption and billing fraud to fleet-scale compromise and grid-impacting load manipulation. Synthesizing evidence across peer-reviewed attacks, empirical deployment analyses, and vendor disclosures, we present six representative EV cyber kill chains that capture how real vulnerabilities compose across layers: ① transaction manipulation leading to billing fraud at scale, ② protocol desynchronization causing persistent charging denial of service, ③ EVSE compromise enabling backend trust abuse and fleet-wide propagation, ④ cloud/API compromise escalating to CSMS privilege and remote command execution, ⑤ firmware downgrade and re-exploitation establishing durable persistence, and ⑥ coordinated EVSE control resulting in synchronized load manipulation with grid impacts.

We distill the ecosystem’s most consequential “missed signals” and derive a prioritized remediation agenda: enforceable security requirements (non-optional secure transport with downgrade-proof negotiation), explicit PLC/PHY threat assumptions, EVSE lifecycle hardening, secured CSMS/OCPP command paths, and grid-aware guardrails against coordinated demand manipulation.

I. INTRODUCTION: HIGHLY INTERCONNECTED EV ECOSYSTEM

ELECTRIC vehicle (EV) charging has evolved into a deeply interconnected *system-of-systems* spanning vehicles, charging stations (EVSE), backend management systems (CSMS), cloud services, and utility networks. These components interact continuously across protocol layers, administrative domains, and physical infrastructures, forming a tightly coupled cyber-physical ecosystem with complex interdependencies.

Problem: While such connectivity enables advanced capabilities, including smart charging, remote operation, and grid

Fig. 1: EV Charging Ecosystem

integration, it also introduces a broad and compositional attack surface. Adversaries can exploit weaknesses across multiple layers rather than within a single component. In practice, vulnerabilities in physical interfaces, communication protocols, backend systems, or timing mechanisms can be combined to form *multi-hop attack paths*, enabling escalation from the charging interface to higher-privilege control planes in cloud and grid-connected systems.

Gaps: Despite the presence of numerous standards and security mechanisms, Table I shows that protections are unevenly distributed and often incomplete. Strong mechanisms such as TLS, PKI-based authentication, and digital signatures exist at specific layers (e.g., ISO 15118, OCPP, IEEE 2030.5), but coexist with components lacking authentication, integrity protection, or enforcement (e.g., IEC 61851, SLAC, IEEE 1588). Furthermore, these protections are rarely validated across layers, leading to implicit trust assumptions, inconsistent enforcement, and exploitable gaps at system boundaries. Existing work typically analyzes vulnerabilities in isolation, without capturing how such gaps can be composed across layers and stakeholders.

Key Insight: We argue that EV cybersecurity is fundamentally a *cross-layer composition problem*, where system-level risk arises from chaining individually valid but collectively insufficient security mechanisms across the ecosystem.

Contribution: To address this challenge, we introduce an attacker-centric *EV Cyber Kill Chain* that models how adversaries escalate from initial access at the charging interface

TABLE I: EV Charging Ecosystem Protocols, Cybersecurity Protections, and Security Gaps Across Layers

Interaction	Protocol	Description	Cybersecurity Asset	Cybersecurity Protection	Gaps / Challenges
EVSE ↔ Cloud	OCPP 2.0.1	Backend connectivity	Comm. channel, endpoints	TLS (server-auth), optional mTLS (X.509), message integrity validation	No visibility beyond endpoints; proxy/intermediate manipulation undetected
EV ↔ Station	ISO 15118	Charging control + billing	EVCC–SECC session, PKI certs, metering data	TLS V2G session, PKI mutual auth, XML DSig (SignedMeteringData) for integrity + non-repudiation	Relies on semantic correctness and timing; no cross-layer validation
	J1772 / IEC 61851	Physical charging interface	Electrical interface, PWM	No cryptographic protection; physical-layer safety only	No auth/integrity; vulnerable to signal manipulation
	SLAC (HPGP)	PLC link setup	NMK/NID association	Unauthenticated SLAC handshake; no integrity or auth	MITM risk during association; weak trust establishment
	SAE J2931-7	Security requirements	Security requirements	Specification only; no enforcement	Depends on implementation; no guarantees
EV Internal	SAE J2836 / J2847	Charging logic/messages	Protocol logic, messages	Relies on ISO 15118 session security	No independent protection; inherits upstream weaknesses
	SAE J2293	Architecture definition	System architecture	No enforcement; design guidance only	No defined trust boundary or runtime security
Cloud ↔ Grid	IEEE 2030.5	Utility coordination	Comm. channel, endpoints	TLS (server auth), X.509 identity validation	Limited cross-domain validation; endpoint trust assumed
	OpenADR	Demand-response signals	Events, control msgs	XML DSig, TLS confidentiality, replay protection (timestamp/nonce)	Replay/timing assumptions exploitable
	IEEE 1547	Grid interconnection	Electrical systems	No cybersecurity controls	No protection for cyber-physical interaction
Cross-Layer Security	IEC 62351	Power comm security	Channels, identities	TLS profiles, X.509 auth, integrity via DSig/MAC	No end-to-end semantic protection across layers
	FIPS 140-3	Crypto validation	Crypto modules	CMVP-certified crypto implementations	Does not address protocol misuse/integration flaws
	RFC 8915 (NTS)	Secure time sync	Time service	TLS key exchange, AEAD-protected time packets	Higher-layer timing dependencies remain exposed
	IEEE 1588	Precision timing	Timing messages	No native auth/integrity	Vulnerable to spoofing, delay, replay attacks
Site Electrical	IEC 60364	Installation rules	Electrical infra	No cybersecurity mechanisms	No cyber protection despite physical dependency
	IEC 62305	Lightning protection	Physical infra	No cybersecurity mechanisms	Only environmental protection
	IEC 61439	Power distribution	Distribution systems	No cybersecurity mechanisms	No cyber-physical threat coverage
Site OT	IEC 62443	OT security framework	Zones, conduits	Segmentation, access control, defense-in-depth	Integration complexity; incomplete coverage
	NERC CIP-006	Physical security	Critical assets	Physical access control, monitoring, logging	No logical/network-layer protection
Lifecycle	ISO/SAE 21434	Cybersecurity lifecycle	Systems, processes	TARA, secure design, validation controls	Process-focused; no runtime enforcement guarantee
	UNECE R155 / R156	Regulatory cybersecurity	Org. processes, systems	CSMS/SUMS governance	High-level; limited technical enforcement
	GB / AIS	Regional regulations	Regional systems	Mandatory compliance	Inconsistent enforcement depth
Operational	ChargePoint Protect	EVSE tamper protection	Cable, hardware	Tamper detection, alerts, alarms	No protocol-level protection

through communication protocols, EVSE control, and backend authority. To our knowledge, this is the first work that models EV charging attack progression as cross-layer exploit chains grounded in real-world vulnerabilities. Specifically, we:

- Expose recurring *multi-hop exploit patterns* driven by fragmented security enforcement,
- Identify *systemic cross-layer gaps* and implicit trust assumptions across stakeholders, and
- Derive *prioritized, enforceable security requirements* for end-to-end protection.

Table I further shows that, despite strong pointwise protections, the EV ecosystem lacks consistent end-to-end guar-

antees, enabling adversaries to traverse layers and construct multi-hop attack chains.

II. EV CHARGING ATTACK SURFACES ACROSS THE CONTROL-AUTHORITY CHAIN

EV charging security spans multiple control domains, including Internet-facing applications and APIs, EV–EVSE session establishment, bidirectional energy negotiation, CSMS fleet command and control, and grid/aggregator interaction [1]–[3]. Fig. 2 presents a taxonomy of attack surfaces across these interfaces. **API attacks** exploit weaknesses in identity, authorization, and session management (e.g., BOLA,

Fig. 2: Taxonomy of Attacks in EV Charging Ecosystem

broken authentication, misconfiguration) to expose sensitive data (PII, tokens) and indirectly trigger unauthorized charger or vehicle actions [3], [4]. **G2V attacks** target the EV–EVSE communication stack (IEC 61851 and ISO 15118 over PLC/Green PHY), enabling manipulation of negotiation, metering, or availability through protocol/state abuse or EVSE compromise [5], [6]. **V2G attacks** extend these weaknesses to bidirectional energy transfer enabled by ISO 15118-20, where integrity of scheduling, metering, and certificate governance becomes critical to prevent unauthorized discharge, fraud, or coordinated disruption [7], [8]. **CSMS attacks** exploit centralized backend authority via OCPP command channels (e.g., remote operations, configuration, firmware updates), where weak authentication or validation enables command spoofing and large-scale control across EVSE fleets [9], [10]. **G2F attacks** leverage system-level coupling between charging infrastructure and grid operations, enabling disruption through coordinated load manipulation, dependency outages, or malicious control signals, which require validated inputs and bounded execution to mitigate impact [1], [11].

III. VULNERABILITY LANDSCAPE ACROSS THE EV CHARGING ECOSYSTEM

Publicly disclosed EV-charging vulnerabilities organize into recurring attacker workflows spanning web/local management interfaces, credential and cryptographic weaknesses, information disclosure, firmware/update integrity failures, adjacent/proximity interfaces (e.g., BLE), EV–EVSE protocol handling, backend command authority, and controller-level hardening. Grounded in the CVEs summarized in Tables II and III, this landscape is structured by *layer*, showing how weaknesses manifest across Web UI, BLE, ISO 15118, backend, firmware, and controller domains. High-impact exploitation arises from the **composition of vulnerabilities across layers**, rather than isolated flaws. The evidence shows that conventional IT weaknesses (e.g., XSS/CSRF/SSRF, credential failures) combine with embedded-system vulnerabilities (e.g., memory corruption, parser weaknesses, resource exhaustion), enabling end-to-

end attack paths from initial access to persistent compromise and fleet-scale impact.

A. Web UI & Local Management: Injection, Session Riding, and Request Pivoting

Web-facing management interfaces expose direct control paths, where injection, session hijacking, and request pivoting flaws (e.g., XSS, CSRF, SSRF, authentication gaps) enable unauthorized EVSE actions and backend abuse [12]–[14]. These weaknesses demonstrate that browser-layer defects translate into persistent operator compromise, session control, and fleet-impacting actions.

B. Credentials & Weak Crypto: Administrative Collapse and Persistent Access

Credential and cryptographic weaknesses (e.g., hard-coded credentials, weak entropy, session mismanagement) eliminate authentication barriers and enable immediate administrative takeover with persistence across sessions [15]–[17]. Reuse of credentials across deployments further amplifies impact from single-device compromise to fleet-wide exposure.

C. Information Disclosure: Enabling Cross-Layer Compromise

Information disclosure (e.g., credential leakage, identity exposure, cleartext storage) acts as a critical enabler for follow-on attacks by lowering the barrier to privilege escalation and lateral movement [18]–[20]. These leaks frequently bridge system layers, transforming reconnaissance into active exploitation.

D. Firmware/Update Security: Downgrade and Trust-Anchor Erosion

Weak firmware lifecycle controls (e.g., insecure updates, rollback, fallback credentials) erode system trust by enabling reintroduction of known vulnerabilities and undermining update integrity [21], [22]. This *trust-anchor erosion* allows persistent compromise even in systems that appear patched.

TABLE II: Publicly disclosed vulnerabilities and incident-derived impacts in the EV charging ecosystem (CVSS v3.x, CWE-Mapped)

CVE	Layer	CVSS	CWE	Damage Impact
<i>Web UI & Local Management</i>				
CVE-2018-7801	Web UI	8.8	CWE-94:Code Injection	Charging infrastructure can be taken over, allowing unauthorized start/stop of EV charging and misuse of energy resources
CVE-2021-22706	Web UI	6.1	CWE-79:Improper Neutralization of Input	Charging session hijack possible via user impersonation, enabling unauthorized charging control
CVE-2021-22723	Web UI	6.1	CWE-79:Improper Neutralization of Input	Charging configuration can be altered without driver knowledge, affecting billing and behavior
CVE-2021-22726	Web UI	8.1	CWE-918:Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF)	Charging system abused to access internal network resources, increasing risk of wider compromise
CVE-2021-22821	Web UI	8.6	CWE-918:Server-Side Request Forgery (SSRF)	Charging backend systems may be accessed or attacked indirectly through charger
CVE-2021-22822	Web UI	6.1	CWE-79:Improper Neutralization of Input	Charging sessions can be modified or stopped without authorization
CVE-2022-22808	Web UI	8.8	CWE-352:Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF)	Charging session hijack leading to unauthorized charging or charging theft
CVE-2024-21550	Web UI	6.1	CWE-79:Improper Neutralization of Input	Charging management interface compromised affecting multiple stations and users
CVE-2024-25407	Backend	7.5	CWE-331:Insufficient Entropy	Active EV charging can be disrupted or stopped (denial of service)
CVE-2024-44843	Backend	5.9	CWE-287:Improper Authentication	Charging sessions may be hijacked without valid authentication
<i>Credentials & Weak Crypto</i>				
CVE-2021-22707	EVSE	9.8	CWE-798:Use of Hard-coded Credentials	Full administrative access enables large-scale charging misuse
CVE-2021-22727	EVSE	9.8	CWE-331:Insufficient Entropy	Weak security allows unauthorized access affecting multiple chargers
CVE-2021-22729	EVSE	9.8	CWE-259:Use of Hard-coded Password	Charging stations can be taken over enabling charging theft
CVE-2021-22730	EVSE	9.8	CWE-798:Use of Hard-coded Credentials	Charging infrastructure compromised enabling unauthorized energy usage
CVE-2021-22774	EVSE	7.5	CWE-916:Use of Weak Password Hashing	Compromised credentials allow charging session hijack
CVE-2021-22820	EVSE	9.8	CWE-613:Insufficient Session Expiration	Hijacked charging session persists even after password change
CVE-2024-43659	EVSE	7.2	CWE-798:Use of Hard-coded Credentials	Fleet-wide compromise enabling large-scale charging fraud
<i>Information Disclosure</i>				
CVE-2021-22728	EVSE	6.5	CWE-200:Exposure of Sensitive Information	Credentials leaked enabling unauthorized access to chargers
CVE-2021-34589	Controller	7.5	CWE-200:Exposure of Sensitive Information	Driver identity (RFID) leaked leading to potential charging theft
CVE-2024-8070	Firmware	8.5	CWE-312:Cleartext Storage of Sensitive Information	Credentials exposed allowing unauthorized charging usage and billing fraud
<i>Firmware / Update Security</i>				
CVE-2024-23958	Firmware	8.8	CWE-798:Use of Hard-coded Credentials	Nearby attacker can access charger and interfere with EV charging
CVE-2025-5825	Firmware	7.5	CWE-1328:Insecure Firmware Rollback (Downgrade)	Firmware downgrade enables long-term compromise of charging system
<i>Adjacent Interfaces (BLE)</i>				
CVE-2023-0863	BLE	8.8	CWE-287:Improper Authentication	Charging sessions can be disrupted or hijacked by nearby attacker
CVE-2023-0864	BLE	4.3	CWE-319:Cleartext Transmission of Sensitive Information	Sensitive setup data exposed during charging configuration
CVE-2024-7391	BLE	5.7	CWE-200:Exposure of Sensitive Information	Wi-Fi credentials leaked enabling further attacks on charging network
CVE-2024-7392	BLE	6.5	CWE-410:Uncontrolled Resource Consumption	Charging station unavailable causing EV charging disruption
CVE-2024-23957	BLE	8.8	CWE-121: Stack-based Buffer Overflow; CWE-787: Out-of-bounds Write	Charging process disrupted or attacker gains full control
CVE-2024-23959	BLE	8.0	CWE-121: Stack-based Buffer Overflow; CWE-787: Out-of-bounds Write	Charging sessions hijacked through Bluetooth attack
CVE-2024-23967	BLE	8.0	CWE-121: Stack-based Buffer Overflow; CWE-787: Out-of-bounds Write	Charger crash disrupts EV charging session
CVE-2024-7795	BLE	8.8	CWE-121: Stack-based Buffer Overflow; CWE-119: Bounds Restriction Failure	Attacker executes code on charger impacting operations
CVE-2025-5826	BLE	6.3	CWE-115:Improper Input Interpretation	Charging commands manipulated affecting charging behavior
CVE-2024-23938	BLE	8.8	CWE-121: Stack-based Buffer Overflow; CWE-787: Out-of-bounds Write	Full system takeover disrupting charging infrastructure
CVE-2025-5747	BLE	8.0	CWE-115:Improper Input Interpretation	Charging behavior altered through crafted inputs
CVE-2025-5824	BLE	7.5	CWE-346:Improper Origin Validation	Unauthorized device interferes with charging session
CVE-2025-5830	BLE	8.8	CWE-122:Heap-Based Buffer Overflow	Full takeover enabling charging fraud and disruption

E. Adjacent Interfaces (BLE/Local Protocols): Proximity Entry and Code Execution

Adjacent interfaces (e.g., BLE, local protocols) provide realistic entry points where weak authentication, information leakage, and memory corruption enable takeover and disruption

[23]–[25]. These interfaces are critical initial footholds for cross-layer attack progression.

TABLE III: CVEs Applicable to the EV Charging Ecosystem (Contd.)

CVE	Layer	CVSS	CWE	Damage Impact
<i>EV-EVSE Protocol Stack (ISO 15118)</i>				
CVE-2022-0878	ISO15118	6.5	CWE-306:Missing Authentication for Critical Function	Charging of electric vehicle disrupted due to communication failure
CVE-2022-27242	ISO15118	5.5	CWE-120:Buffer Overflow	Charging process stops due to system crash
CVE-2026-24003	ISO15118	4.3	CWE-287: Improper Authentication; CWE-863: Incorrect Authorization	Charging sequence manipulated leading to incorrect operation
CVE-2025-12357	ISO15118	8.3	CWE-923:Improper Communication Channel Restriction	Charging session intercepted allowing manipulation or hijacking
CVE-2025-24956	ISO15118	9.8	CWE-120:Buffer Overflow	Charging disrupted or system takeover during operation
CVE-2025-68133	ISO15118	7.4	CWE-770:Uncontrolled Resource Consumption	Charging unavailable due to system overload
CVE-2025-27071	ISO15118	8.8	CWE-120:Buffer Overflow	Attacker achieves code execution via SLAC protocol, enabling EV-EVSE communication control and potential session takeover
<i>Backend Control</i>				
CVE-2024-23920	Backend	8.8	CWE-284:Improper Access Control	Unauthorized control over EV charging operations
CVE-2024-23921	Backend	8.8	CWE-94:Code Injection	Charging behavior manipulated via remote commands
CVE-2024-23968	Backend	8.8	CWE-120:Buffer Overflow	Charging disruption due to system crash
CVE-2024-23970	Backend	6.5	CWE-295:Improper Certificate Validation	Charging communication intercepted or altered
CVE-2025-54564	Backend	N/A	CWE-20: Improper Input Validation; CWE-77: Command Injection	Unauthorized commands disrupt charging operations
CVE-2024-23971	Backend	8.8	CWE-77:Command Injection	Charging session hijack via protocol manipulation
CVE-2024-11666	Backend	9.8	CWE-345:Insufficient Data Authenticity Verification	Attacker controls multiple chargers at fleet level
CVE-2025-5822	Backend	8.8	CWE-863:Incorrect Authorization	Privilege escalation enables system-wide control
CVE-2023-52096	Backend	7.5	CWE-89:SQL Injection	Charging and billing data manipulated leading to fraud
<i>Controller OS</i>				
CVE-2021-34591	Controller	7.8	CWE-250:Execution with Unnecessary Privileges	Full charger system control affecting availability
CVE-2021-34592	Controller	8.8	CWE-77:Command Injection	Charging behavior altered through system commands
CVE-2021-34601	Controller	9.8	CWE-798; CWE-259:Hardcoded Credentials	Remote admin access enables misuse of charging system
CVE-2021-34602	Controller	8.8	CWE-78:OS Command Injection	Full system control impacts EV charging operations

F. EV-EVSE Protocol Stack: Parser Robustness and State Integrity

Protocol-layer weaknesses (e.g., missing authentication, parser flaws, state-machine inconsistencies) directly affect charging correctness and availability [26]–[28]. Exploitation at pre-auth and negotiation stages enables session disruption and control before higher-layer protections apply.

G. Backend Command Authority: Fleet-Scale Control Risks

Backend vulnerabilities in access control, command validation, and transport integrity enable adversaries to issue or manipulate commands across EVSE fleets [29]–[31]. Centralized control amplifies localized weaknesses into system-wide impact.

H. Charge Controller OS / Field Device Hardening

Controller-level weaknesses (e.g., privilege escalation, command injection, hard-coded credentials) expose direct execution paths and collapse trust boundaries at the device layer [32]–[34]. Robust field-device hardening is therefore essential to prevent compromise propagation across the ecosystem.

IV. THE EV CYBER KILL CHAIN: FROM CHARGING PORT TO CLOUD

Prior EVSE security analyses characterize vulnerabilities by interface or layer but do not capture how they compose in

practice. In real deployments, adversaries exploit misaligned assumptions across layers to construct cross-domain attack chains with operational impact.

We introduce the *EV Cyber Kill Chain* as an attacker-centric model that captures how vulnerabilities are *operationally chained* across layers. It links layer transitions (e.g., BLE → ISO 15118 → CSMS), control escalation (device → fleet → grid-adjacent), attack objectives (disruption, fraud, persistence, grid manipulation), and assumption violations (trusted pairing, protocol correctness, backend authority).

Grounded in disclosed vulnerabilities (Tables II–III), the model shows that system-level risk arises from cross-layer composition, where locally enforced but inconsistent controls can be combined into multi-stage attack paths. Compromises can originate at diverse entry points, propagate across protocol and control layers, and leverage backend authority for scaled impact. To validate these chains, we map representative CVEs to attack steps and resulting outcomes (Table IV). All CVEs in this mapping are derived from Tables II–III, providing a traceable and evidence-based linkage between disclosed weaknesses and end-to-end exploit paths. Overall, EV charging security is constrained less by the absence of controls than by the lack of consistent *end-to-end enforcement*, enabling adversaries to traverse layers and achieve high-impact outcomes.

Fig. 3: Chain 1: Transaction Manipulation Leading to Charging Fraud at Scale

A. Chain 1: Transaction Manipulation Leading to Charging Fraud at Scale

Objective: Billing manipulation and unauthorized energy usage across multiple chargers

The attack chain spans *Local/Proximity*, *Credential/Access*, *EVSE Control*, and *Backend/CSMS* layers, combining local interface exposure, credential leakage, weak authentication, and lack of transaction validation to manipulate charging sessions and billing outcomes at scale as shown in Fig. 3. **Pre-conditions:** Exposed or weakly secured local interfaces (e.g., BLE commissioning), presence of credential leakage paths (cleartext/insecure storage), weak authentication (default/hard-coded credentials or weak session controls), and insufficient transaction integrity and cross-layer validation allowing backend acceptance of manipulated billing data. **Constraints:** Requires proximity or access to adjacent/local interfaces for initial foothold, scales only if credentials/admin access are reused or portable across devices, and impact is bounded if strong end-to-end semantic validation and reconciliation controls are enforced in backend billing systems.

Step 1: Enumerate Local Interfaces (BLE Recon): The attacker exploits weak or unauthenticated local interfaces to identify accessible services and configuration surfaces. **Achieved:** Discovery of communication endpoints and exploitable access paths. **Resulting Effect:** Establishes a foothold for interaction and enables subsequent extraction of sensitive artifacts.

Step 2: Extract Credentials (Information Disclosure): The attacker leverages information disclosure (e.g., cleartext transmission or insecure storage—CWE-200, CWE-312) to obtain sensitive artifacts. **Achieved:** Extraction of administrative credentials, Wi-Fi keys, or configuration secrets. **Resulting Effect:** Authentication barriers are bypassed, enabling unauthorized access to EVSE management interfaces.

Step 3: Obtain Administrative Control (EVSE Access): The attacker exploits weak authentication controls (e.g., default or hard-coded credentials, weak credential protection—CWE-798, CWE-259, CWE-916) to elevate privileges. **Achieved:** Privileged administrative access to EVSE control functions. **Resulting Effect:** Direct control over charging sessions and transaction behavior.

Step 4: Manipulate Transactions (OCPP Exploitation): The attacker exploits insufficient transaction integrity validation and weak protocol enforcement in OCPP communication (e.g., improper authentication, predictable identifiers—CWE-287, CWE-331). **Achieved:** Modification of transaction data such as session identifiers, metering values, and start/stop events prior to backend processing. **Resulting Effect:** Decoupling of actual energy delivery from recorded billing data.

Step 5: Tamper Billing Logic (Backend Abuse): The attacker exploits absence of cross-layer validation between EVSE measurements and backend billing systems. **Achieved:** Backend acceptance of manipulated transaction records as legitimate inputs. **Resulting Effect:** Incorrect or zero billing for energy consumption, enabling large-scale charging theft and revenue loss.

B. Chain 2: Protocol Desynchronization Leading to Charging DoS at Scale

Objective: Induce persistent charging failures and degrade availability across sessions and stations

This chain exploits weaknesses in pre-authentication communication, timing/state assumptions, and protocol robustness (unauthenticated SLAC pairing, timing manipulation, validation gaps, and weak recovery/monitoring) to repeatedly desynchronize EV–EVSE state machines and force session aborts, scaling single-session disruption into widespread charging outages as shown in Fig. 4. **Preconditions:** Unauthenticated SLAC pairing enabling pre-auth manipulation, exploitable timing/state dependencies in EV–EVSE communication, insufficient protocol validation/state-machine enforcement in ISO 15118/PLC handling, and weak session recovery and monitoring (no rate-limiting or anomaly detection) allowing repeated desynchronization and aborts. **Constraints:** Requires ability to influence pre-auth SLAC/early message exchange (e.g., proximity for injection/delay/replay), scales only if attacks can be automated and repeated across sessions/fleet, and impact is bounded in deployments with pairing anomaly detection, rate-limiting, and cross-layer telemetry/monitoring.

Step 1: Disrupt SLAC Pairing (Pre-Auth Entry): The attacker exploits the lack of authentication and integrity in SLAC pairing to interfere with EV–EVSE association. **Achieved:**

Fig. 4: Chain 2: Protocol Desynchronization Leading to Charging DoS at Scale

Ability to disrupt or manipulate network association attempts. **Resulting Effect:** Establishes influence before secure session establishment, enabling repeated pairing failures and unstable session initiation.

Step 2: Induce Timing Desynchronization (Message Delay/Replay): The attacker manipulates timing-sensitive exchanges by delaying, replaying, or reordering critical handshake messages. **Achieved:** Controlled message timing and sequencing disruptions. **Resulting Effect:** EV and EVSE state machines desynchronize (“Sync Lost”), preventing consistent progression to a stable charging session.

Step 3: Inject Protocol Inconsistency (Message Manipulation): The attacker exploits insufficient input validation and state-machine enforcement in ISO 15118/PLC handling using malformed, replayed, or out-of-sequence messages. **Achieved:** Injection of inconsistent protocol inputs during negotiation or operation. **Resulting Effect:** Parser errors and invalid transitions accumulate, destabilizing the EVSE control stack and increasing session failure likelihood.

Step 4: Trigger Session Abort (State Machine Failure): The attacker repeatedly drives the system into error handling paths that lack resilience to abnormal protocol behavior. **Achieved:** Reliable triggering of session abort conditions. **Resulting Effect:** Sessions fail to initialize or terminate prematurely, creating repeated connection failures and sustained denial of charging.

Step 5: Amplify Failures at Scale (Fleet-Wide Disruption): The attacker leverages repeatability across deployments plus missing rate-limiting/anomaly detection to automate disruption across many sessions and stations. **Achieved:** Repeated exploitation across multiple EV–EVSE interactions. **Resulting Effect:** Widespread establishment failures and persistent out-of-service conditions, degrading charging availability at fleet or site scale.

C. Chain 3: EVSE Compromise Leading to Backend Abuse and Fleet Control

Objective: Gain persistent control over chargers and escalate to fleet-level manipulation

This chain progresses from an adjacent foothold to EVSE code execution and persistence, then leverages implicit trust relationships in EVSE-to-CSMS/OCPP control paths to turn a single compromised charger into a backend-enabled force multiplier for multi-station control as shown in Fig. 5. **Pre-conditions:** Presence of exposed adjacent interfaces (e.g., BLE/maintenance/debug), exploitable protocol or memory corruption vulnerabilities enabling code execution on EVSE, absence of lifecycle hardening (no secure boot, signed updates, or strong credential management) allowing persistence, and implicit trust in EVSE-to-CSMS/OCPP communication enabling backend abuse. **Constraints:** Requires at least one initial EVSE foothold to initiate the chain, persistence is constrained if secure boot/anti-rollback/signed update mechanisms are enforced, and fleet-scale impact is bounded by CSMS access controls, segmentation, and least-privilege enforcement. **Step 1: Establish Local Foothold (Interface Access):** The attacker exploits exposed adjacent interfaces or weak local controls (e.g., BLE/maintenance/debug) to interact with EVSE services and deliver crafted inputs. **Achieved:** A usable foothold on EVSE-accessible interfaces. **Resulting Effect:** Enables controlled interaction with lower-level protocol handlers and device control surfaces.

Step 2: Execute Code on EVSE (Protocol Exploitation): The attacker triggers protocol parsing or memory corruption flaws (e.g., ISO 15118/local services; CWE-120, CWE-787) to obtain execution on the controller. **Achieved:** Remote code execution on the EVSE runtime. **Resulting Effect:** Arbitrary control of device logic and communications, enabling manipulation of charging behavior and management interfaces.

Step 3: Persist on Device (Firmware / Credential Backdoor): The attacker exploits weak lifecycle controls (e.g., no

Fig. 5: Chain 3: EVSE Compromise Leading to Backend Abuse and Fleet Control

Fig. 6: Chain 4: Cloud/API Compromise Enabling Direct Fleet Command (Cloud-First Control)

secure boot, insecure update mechanisms, hard-coded credentials; CWE-798, CWE-1328) to maintain long-lived access. **Achieved:** Persistent presence via firmware modification or backdoor installation. **Resulting Effect:** Compromise survives reboots, routine maintenance, and standard recovery workflows.

Step 4: Abuse Backend Trust (CSMS Interaction): The attacker leverages implicit trust in EVSE-to-CSMS channels (insufficient endpoint validation / weak authorization; CWE-284, CWE-287) to operate as a trusted endpoint. **Achieved:** Ability to send/receive backend commands using the compromised EVSE identity and channel. **Resulting Effect:** Backend workflows amplify attacker actions beyond a single charger through authorized-looking command paths.

Step 5: Scale Control Across Fleet (Command Propagation): The attacker exploits centralized backend authority to push malicious or abusive actions across managed assets. **Achieved:** Command propagation to additional EVSEs. **Resulting Effect:** Coordinated multi-station control and dis-

tributed infrastructure compromise driven by backend reach.

D. Chain 4: Cloud/API Compromise Enabling Direct Fleet Command (Cloud-First Control)

Objective: Achieve fleet-wide control via backend compromise without local EVSE access

This chain begins with cloud/API exposure and escalates through authorization weaknesses to obtain CSMS-level privileges, enabling attacker-issued commands to execute at scale over trusted backend-to-device control channels as shown in Fig. 6. **Preconditions:** Presence of vulnerable cloud-facing APIs (broken authentication, session/token mismanagement), weak authorization enabling privilege escalation to CSMS admin functions, insufficient command validation/integrity checks in backend-to-EVSE workflows, and centralized CSMS orchestration enabling large-scale command execution. **Constraints:** Requires valid or forged backend sessions/tokens to initiate, impact is bounded if strong RBAC/least-privilege and

Fig. 7: Chain 5: Firmware Downgrade Leading to Persistent Backdoor Control

separation of duties are enforced, and sustained fleet-wide abuse is constrained in environments with centralized logging, monitoring, and anomaly detection.

Step 1: Gain Cloud Access (API Exploitation): The attacker exploits cloud-facing API weaknesses (e.g., broken authentication, session mismanagement, insecure token handling; CWE-287, CWE-613) to obtain unauthorized backend access.

Achieved: Access to backend services via stolen or forged sessions/tokens. **Resulting Effect:** Establishes a cloud-level foothold with visibility into APIs and operational control surfaces.

Step 2: Escalate Privileges (CSMS Access): The attacker exploits insufficient authorization controls or weak privilege separation (e.g., improper role validation; CWE-284) to gain administrative capabilities. **Achieved:** Elevated access to CSMS management functions. **Resulting Effect:** Enables direct interaction with EVSE management workflows, including command issuance and configuration control.

Step 3: Issue Authorized Commands (OCPP Abuse): The attacker abuses trusted backend-to-device control channels where command validation/integrity checks are weak (CWE-345). **Achieved:** Ability to issue legitimate-looking commands (start/stop, limit power, firmware updates) via CSMS. **Resulting Effect:** Direct manipulation of charging sessions and device behavior across connected EVSEs.

Step 4: Execute Fleet-Wide Actions (Centralized Control): The attacker uses centralized orchestration to apply actions concurrently across multiple assets. **Achieved:** Coordinated command execution across many EVSEs. **Resulting Effect:** Fleet-scale disruption or misuse (e.g., session manipulation, unauthorized configuration/updates) without requiring device-level compromise.

E. Chain 5: Firmware Downgrade Leading to Persistent Backdoor Control

Objective: Establish long-term, stealthy control by eroding lifecycle trust

This chain exploits rollback-capable update processes to reintroduce known-vulnerable firmware, then leverages weak

integrity enforcement to implant a durable backdoor that persists across reboots and updates as shown in Fig. 7. **Preconditions:** Firmware downgrade is possible due to lack of anti-rollback and update validation, downgraded images contain known exploitable vulnerabilities enabling code execution, absence of secure boot and integrity protections allows backdoor implantation and persistence, and lack of continuous integrity verification enables stealthy long-term control. **Constraints:** Requires a practical path to trigger firmware update/downgrade mechanisms, persistence is constrained if secure boot, signed updates, metadata validation, and anti-rollback are enforced, and stealth control is bounded in environments with auditable update channels and integrity monitoring.

Step 1: Downgrade Firmware (Lifecycle Abuse): The attacker exploits weak update controls and missing anti-rollback protections (e.g., insecure version enforcement / update validation; CWE-494, CWE-1328) to install an older image. **Achieved:** Installation of a vulnerable firmware version on the EVSE. **Resulting Effect:** Previously patched weaknesses are reintroduced, weakening the device security posture and reopening exploit paths.

Step 2: Re-Exploit Known Vulnerabilities (Code Execution): The attacker triggers known flaws present in the downgraded firmware (e.g., memory corruption, improper input validation; CWE-120, CWE-787). **Achieved:** Arbitrary code execution on the EVSE controller. **Resulting Effect:** Full runtime compromise under legacy conditions that may evade operational expectations tied to patched behavior.

Step 3: Implant Persistent Backdoor (Integrity Bypass): The attacker leverages absent secure boot or weak firmware/file integrity checks (e.g., CWE-353, CWE-494) to introduce unauthorized modifications. **Achieved:** Persistent backdoor placement within firmware or system components. **Resulting Effect:** Long-term control that survives reboots and routine maintenance while undermining trust in device software state.

Step 4: Maintain Covert Control (Stealth Persistence): The attacker relies on implicit runtime trust and lack of continuous integrity verification to remain undetected. **Achieved:** Sus-

Fig. 8: Chain 6: EVSE and Backend Control Enabling Coordinated Load Manipulation and Grid Impact

tained covert access and control over compromised EVSEs. **Resulting Effect:** Persistent manipulation capability that erodes higher-layer security mechanisms dependent on a trusted device baseline.

F. Chain 6: EVSE and Backend Control Enabling Coordinated Load Manipulation and Grid Impact

Objective: Manipulate aggregate charging load to create grid-adjacent impact

This chain combines EVSE compromise with backend coordination to synchronize charging behavior across many stations, exploiting missing safeguards (rate limiting, anomaly detection, grid-aware constraints) to induce abnormal aggregate load patterns that stress local grid conditions as shown in Fig. 8. **Preconditions:** EVSE control is achieved via compromised devices or weak protections, centralized CSMS authority enables coordinated command execution over trusted EVSE-to-backend channels, absence of safeguards (e.g., rate limiting or anomaly detection) allows synchronized control, and exploitable cyber-physical coupling enables aggregated load manipulation impacting grid dynamics. **Constraints:** Requires control over multiple EVSEs to achieve meaningful grid-level impact, attack effectiveness is constrained if grid-aware guardrails and bounded control policies are enforced, and coordinated manipulation is limited in environments with centralized monitoring, anomaly detection, and detection of synchronized command patterns.

Step 1: Compromise EVSE Control (Device Access): The attacker gains control of EVSE behavior by exploiting weak device protections or prior compromise paths (e.g., CWE-284, CWE-287). **Achieved:** Control over charging parameters and EVSE communications at one or more stations. **Resulting Effect:** Establishes the ability to influence charging behavior locally and to present compromised EVSEs as controllable endpoints.

Step 2: Leverage Backend Authority (CSMS Coordination): The attacker exploits centralized management authority and weak validation in trusted EVSE-to-CSMS channels (e.g., implicit trust / weak authorization; CWE-345, CWE-306).

Achieved: Coordinated command capability across multiple EVSEs via backend control. **Resulting Effect:** Consolidates distributed device control into a centralized mechanism for synchronized action.

Step 3: Synchronize Charging Behavior (Load Manipulation): The attacker exploits lack of safeguards against synchronized or abnormal command execution (no rate limiting, anomaly detection, or grid-aware constraints). **Achieved:** Simultaneous triggering, throttling, or modulation of charging sessions across many EVSEs. **Resulting Effect:** Artificially synchronized load spikes/drops and rapid demand fluctuations at site or regional scale.

Step 4: Impact Grid Dynamics (System-Level Effect): The attacker leverages dependencies between aggregated charging demand and grid stability. **Achieved:** Coordinated influence over grid load through EV charging behavior. **Resulting Effect:** Infrastructure stress or localized outages and potential market/operational disruption driven by manipulated aggregate demand.

V. WHY THESE GAPS PERSIST: THE ECOSYSTEM'S "MISSED SIGNALS"

Current EV charging deployments fail to detect and prevent cross-domain exploit chaining due to systemic, non-technical root causes spanning standards, stakeholder boundaries, validation practices, and operational visibility.

Overreliance on Standards Standards define *expected* secure behavior, but conformance omits adversarial conditions, downgrade paths, and cross-party boundary failures. As a result, deployments claim protocol compliance while remaining vulnerable to link pairing manipulation, parser weaknesses, and backend authority abuse [7], [35], [36].

Misaligned Stakeholder Responsibilities OEMs, EVSE vendors, CSMS operators, roaming providers, and utilities assume another party is responsible for enforcing critical controls (e.g., certificate policies, revocation, identity formats, transport profiles, logging). These gaps manifest in real-world disclosures involving weak credential governance and improper certificate validation [15], [37].

TABLE IV: Mapping and prioritization of representative CVEs to EV Cyber Kill Chain steps demonstrating cross-layer attack composition

Chain	Priority	Step (in chain)	Representative CVEs	Observed Outcome (evidence-backed)
Chain 1 (Fraud)	High	Step 2–3: Credential Extraction → EVSE Access	CVE-2021-22728, CVE-2024-8070, CVE-2021-22707, CVE-2021-22820	Credential leakage, insecure storage, and hard-coded credentials have been shown to allow unauthorized access to EVSE management interfaces, enabling control over charging sessions
	High	Step 4–5: Transaction Manipulation (OCPP / Backend)	CVE-2024-23920, CVE-2024-23971, CVE-2023-52096, CVE-2024-25407	Backend access control and injection weaknesses can allow manipulation of transaction data or identifiers, which may lead to billing inconsistencies or charging misuse
Chain 2 (DoS)	Medium	Step 1: Pre-auth Entry (SLAC / Early Session)	CVE-2022-0878, CVE-2025-27071	Missing authentication and early-stage protocol weaknesses can disrupt EV–EVSE session establishment prior to secure communication setup
	Medium	Step 2–4: Timing / State / Parser Abuse → Session Abort	CVE-2025-68133, CVE-2022-27242, CVE-2026-24003	Resource exhaustion, parsing flaws, and state inconsistencies can trigger repeated session aborts or unstable charging behavior, resulting in denial of service conditions
Chain 3 (Fleet Control)	Critical	Step 1–3: Local Foothold → RCE → Persistence	CVE-2023-0863, CVE-2024-23957, CVE-2025-5825, CVE-2024-23958	Adjacent-interface weaknesses and memory corruption vulnerabilities have been shown to enable code execution on EVSE devices; insecure update or rollback mechanisms may support persistence
	Critical	Step 4–5: Backend Trust Abuse → Fleet Propagation	CVE-2024-11666, CVE-2025-5822, CVE-2024-23920	Backend authentication and authorization weaknesses can allow compromised or malicious entities to interact with CSMS functions, potentially affecting multiple connected EVSEs
Chain 4 (Cloud-First Fleet Command)	Critical	Step 1: Cloud/API Access (Session/Auth Compromise)	CVE-2024-44843, CVE-2024-21550, CVE-2021-22820	Cloud-facing authentication, session, or UI weaknesses can allow unauthorized access to backend-facing interfaces or operator sessions
	Critical	Step 2–4: Privilege Escalation → Command Issuance → Fleet Actions	CVE-2025-5822, CVE-2024-23920, CVE-2025-54564, CVE-2024-23971	Authorization and command validation weaknesses may allow escalation of privileges and issuance of control commands that influence EVSE operations across connected devices
Chain 5 (Downgrade → Persistent Backdoor)	High	Step 1: Downgrade / Rollback to Vulnerable Firmware	CVE-2025-5825	Insecure firmware rollback mechanisms can allow installation of outdated firmware versions, reintroducing previously known vulnerabilities
	High	Step 2–4: Re-exploit → Backdoor → Persistence	CVE-2018-7801, CVE-2024-23957, CVE-2024-23958, CVE-2021-22730	Reintroduced vulnerabilities may enable code execution or privilege misuse, while weak firmware or credential protections can allow continued unauthorized access depending on implementation
Chain 6 (Grid Impact via Coordinated Load Manipulation)	Critical	Step 1: Compromise EVSE Control (Device Access)	CVE-2021-22707, CVE-2024-23957, CVE-2021-34602	Device-level compromise through credential or execution vulnerabilities can provide control over individual EVSE charging behavior
	Critical	Step 2–4: Backend Coordination → Load Synchronization → Grid Impact	CVE-2024-11666, CVE-2024-23920, CVE-2024-23971, CVE-2025-54564	Backend command or authorization weaknesses can enable coordinated control across EVSE fleets, which may result in synchronized charging behavior and potential grid-adjacent effects

Siloed Testing and Limited Adversarial Validation Vehicle, charger, and cloud/API testing are performed in isolation—without integrated EV–EVSE–CSMS environments or adversarial conditions. This fragmentation prevents discovery of cross-layer exploit paths and allows resource exhaustion, protocol inconsistencies, and state desynchronization issues to persist into production [3], [38].

Insufficient Telemetry and Early-Stage Detection Operational monitoring focuses on high-level events but omits early-stage indicators such as repeated pairing attempts, anomalous commissioning activity, or protocol-level fuzzing. Without cross-layer telemetry and correlation, initial compromise remains undetected until it escalates into outages or fraud [3], [39].

Collectively, these gaps enable attackers to traverse layers undetected, allowing early-stage footholds to evolve into cross-domain attack chains with system-level impact.

VI. PRIORITIZED REMEDIATION AGENDA: ENFORCEABLE SECURITY REQUIREMENTS

The EV charging ecosystem shall implement the following non-negotiable, enforceable security requirements across all components and stakeholders.

Requirement 1: Secure Transport with Downgrade Protection All communications shall use mutually authenticated secure transport where specified. Systems shall reject insecure negotiation outcomes and prevent downgrade to weaker security modes.

Requirement 2: End-to-End Trust and PKI A unified end-to-end trust chain shall be enforced across EV, EVSE, CSMS, cloud, and grid interfaces. Certificate issuance, validation, and revocation shall be consistently managed using a defined PKI.

Requirement 3: PLC/PHY Security Enforcement PLC/PHY interactions shall be treated as security boundaries. Systems shall

TABLE V: Enforceable Security Requirements: Stakeholder Mapping and Governance Gaps

Req.	Primary Stakeholders	Enforcement Responsibility	Governance Gap
R1	OEM, EVSE, CSMS	Implement and configure TLS/mTLS where specified; prevent acceptance of insecure or downgraded sessions	Transport security profiles inconsistently configured; downgrade handling often not enforced
R2	OEM, CSMS, eMSP	Manage certificate lifecycle, trust anchors, and revocation across interacting systems	Fragmented PKI ownership and inconsistent revocation enforcement across parties
R3	EVSE, OEM	Validate SLAC/PLC association behavior and detect anomalous or repeated pairing attempts	SLAC/PLC treated as non-security layer; no standard auth or integrity protection
R4	CSMS, OEM, EVSE	Enforce unique identities and authentication mechanisms; restrict unauthorized access	Shared credentials and weak authentication practices persist in deployments
R5	EVSE	Support secure boot, signed firmware updates, and rollback protection where capable	Many deployed EVSE lack hardware root of trust or enforceable update integrity
R6	Site Owner, Operator	Implement network segmentation and control remote access pathways	Security dependent on site configuration rather than product-level enforcement
R7	CSMS, EVSE	Validate and authorize OCPP or backend-issued commands before execution	Backend systems often implicitly trusted; command validation inconsistent
R8	CSMS, Fleet	Collect and monitor logs; detect anomalies across EVSE and backend systems	Limited visibility into early-stage or cross-layer attack indicators
R9	OEM, CSMS	Protect sensitive data in transit and at rest; enforce access restrictions	Inconsistent data protection practices across backend and cloud systems
R10	EVSE, Site Owner	Implement tamper detection and restrict physical and local interface access where feasible	Physical and cyber protections typically not integrated or correlated
R11	Utility, CSMS, Aggregator	Validate external control signals and constrain execution within safe operating bounds	Lack of standardized validation or enforcement across grid-facing interfaces
R12	OEM, EVSE, CSMS	Track vulnerabilities, apply updates, and coordinate remediation activities	Responsibility fragmented; patch timelines and ownership unclear
R13	OEM, Tier-1	Require supplier compliance and validate delivered software/hardware artifacts	Limited transparency and verification across supply chain tiers
R14	CSMS, Fleet	Establish detection, response, and recovery processes across operations	Cross-entity coordination and responsibility boundaries often undefined
R15	OEM, EVSE	Apply threat analysis (TARA) and secure development practices during design and validation	Inconsistent adoption and limited enforcement across vendors
R16	All stakeholders	Define roles, responsibilities, and compliance expectations across ecosystem interactions	Ownership and accountability not clearly defined across stakeholders

enforce endpoint binding, replay protection where applicable, and detection and rate-limiting of anomalous pairing attempts.

Requirement 4: Identity and Access Control All entities shall use unique identities. Systems shall enforce strong authentication, eliminate shared or default credentials, and apply least privilege access controls across all interfaces.

Requirement 5: EVSE Secure Lifecycle EVSE shall enforce secure boot, signed firmware updates, integrity validation, and anti-rollback protection. Only authenticated and verified updates shall be accepted and deployed.

Requirement 6: Network Segmentation and Remote Access Security Networks shall be segmented to prevent lateral movement. All remote access shall require strong authentication, encrypted channels, and full session logging. Direct external exposure shall be minimized.

Requirement 7: Secured Command and Control Paths All CSMS and OCPP command paths shall enforce authentication, authorization, and message integrity validation. Control plane functions shall be isolated from monitoring and user interfaces.

Requirement 8: Logging and Continuous Monitoring Systems shall generate tamper-resistant logs for security-relevant events and transmit them to centralized monitoring systems. Real-time monitoring and anomaly detection shall be enforced.

Requirement 9: Data Protection and Privacy All sensitive data shall be encrypted at rest and in transit. Data collection shall be minimized, access shall be restricted, and lifecycle controls for retention and deletion shall be enforced.

Requirement 10: Physical and Cyber-Physical Security EVSE

hardware shall enforce tamper resistance, controlled physical access, and monitoring of unauthorized access events. Debug interfaces and removable media access shall be restricted or disabled.

Requirement 11: Grid Interaction Safety Controls External control signals shall be validated before execution. Systems shall enforce bounded operation and safe fallback modes under failure or communication loss conditions.

Requirement 12: Vulnerability Management Systems shall implement continuous vulnerability identification, assessment, and remediation. Exposure to known vulnerabilities shall be minimized through timely updates and mitigations.

Requirement 13: Supply Chain Security All suppliers and third parties shall comply with defined cybersecurity requirements. Hardware and software integrity shall be verified prior to deployment.

Requirement 14: Incident Response and Recovery Systems shall implement defined incident detection, response, and recovery procedures. Operations shall support isolation, containment, and restoration following compromise.

Requirement 15: Security-by-Design Cybersecurity requirements shall be incorporated during system design, development, and validation. Threat modeling and security testing shall be performed prior to deployment.

Requirement 16: Governance and Continuous Assurance Organizations shall define security roles, responsibilities, and accountability. Systems shall be periodically assessed and updated to address evolving threats and standards.

VII. DEPLOYMENT FEASIBILITY: FROM REQUIREMENTS TO PRACTICE

The proposed requirements must be applied within heterogeneous EVSE deployments. We distinguish between *greenfield systems*, where security can be built-in, and *brownfield systems*, where legacy constraints limit immediate adoption. Existing EVSE often lack secure boot, hardware roots of trust, and robust update paths, constraining deployment of controls such as mutual authentication and signed firmware. In such environments, retrofit feasibility is bounded by device capabilities.

Practical adoption therefore relies on incremental controls, including network segmentation, gateway-enforced protections (e.g., TLS termination), credential hardening, and backend validation. Operational constraints further impact feasibility: EVSE are uptime-critical, distributed, and vendor-diverse, making intrusive updates and strict enforcement operationally and economically costly. These factors necessitate a staged approach—immediate risk reduction via compensating controls in brownfield systems, and full requirement adoption in greenfield deployments—positioning the requirements as enforceable targets under real-world constraints.

VIII. CONCLUSION

EV charging is no longer a single product boundary; it is a cyber-physical ecosystem whose security depends on consistent enforcement of cross-domain requirements across vehicles, EVSE, backend systems, and grid-adjacent interfaces. By systematizing the disclosed CVE landscape into a practical attack taxonomy and introducing an attacker-centric EV Cyber Kill Chain, this paper demonstrates how weaknesses spanning commissioning interfaces, protocol layers, firmware lifecycle controls, backend APIs, and CSMS authority paths compose into multi-stage exploit chains.

These chains demonstrate that high-impact outcomes—fraud, disruption, persistence, and grid-level effects—emerge from cross-layer exploitability rather than isolated vulnerabilities. As a result, system-level risk is driven not by the absence of individual controls, but by inconsistent enforcement and implicit trust assumptions across layers and stakeholders.

The remediation agenda is therefore not “more controls,” but enforceable ecosystem requirements: downgrade-proof secure transport, explicit PLC/PHY threat modeling, lifecycle trust hardening, secured command authority, and grid-aware operational guardrails. Achieving resilient EV charging infrastructure requires shifting from component-level security to verifiable end-to-end assurance across the entire control plane.

IX. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We thank AUTO-ISAC for sharing the automotive-relevant subset of CVEs, which was reviewed and referenced to inform the vulnerability landscape discussed in this work. We also thank Chris S. York, Senior Security Advisor at Cummins Inc., for his valuable review and feedback.

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